

A Performance Comparison Of C# 2013, Delphi XE6, And Python 3.4 Languages

Abdulkadir KARACI¹

¹Department of Computer Engineering, Kastamonu University, Kastamonu, Turkey

ABSTRACT

C# 2013, Delphi XE6, and Python 3.4 are the newest and most popular programming languages. These programming languages become more popular every passing day. In this study, the response times, memory usages, and code lengths of these languages were tested in various workloads. Whether or not there was any significant difference between the data obtained from workloads was tested via the Friedman test. The test indicated a significant difference. In addition, the Wilcoxon signed rank test was used for determining the effect size. This test showed that the level of the significant difference found in the Friedman test was high.

KEYWORDS

C#, Delphi XE6, Performance Test, Python, Programming Language

1.INTRODUCTION

Most of the developers are choosing the managed programming language. Because, managed language has the following features.

1. Data and memory type safety,
2. Perform the automatic memory management,
3. Dynamic code transmission

Further, most of these programming languages are object-oriented programming languages [1]. The languages C# 2013, Delphi XE6 are managed languages. The Python is unmanaged language. Memory method of unmanaged programming languages is not automatic. Therefore they are not safe.

Microsoft .NET platform has provided a robust framework. Thus, Windows applications have been developed so much easier. [2]. The NET Framework is a complete “application” development platform, which has been developed by the Microsoft and, which has been established on open Internet protocols and standards. The scope of application concept here is very broad. Everything from a desktop application to a web browser has been considered within this platform and everything has been supported. [3].

Programmers and computer scientists conduct research on the advantages and disadvantages of various programming languages. Gillings and compared C, C++, C#, Java, Perl, and Python languages in terms of memory usage and speed of execution by using 3 standard bioinformatics methods. C was found to be the strongest [4]. Arudchelvam et al. compared FORTRAN, C, and Java programming languages in terms of memory usage and run-time. These three languages were found to be equal in terms of run-time. FORTRAN was found to be using less memory [5]. Lutz Prechelt compared C, C++, Java, Perl, Python, Rexx, and Tcl programming languages in terms of program length, programming effort, runtime efficiency, memory consumption, and

reliability [6]. Konstantin Berlin et al. compared Pthreads, OpenMP, MPI, and UPC parallel computing APIs [7].

To contribute to works in this field, C# 2013, Delphi XE6, and Python 3.4 programming languages were compared in terms of response time, memory usage, and code length in the present study. These programming languages were chosen because they are popular and commonly used.

2. EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

Of the 400 research articles in software engineering, which need experimental validation, 40% do not include experiment at all and this ratio in other disciplines 15% [8]. Therefore, in this article, in order to test the performance of programming languages, experimental algorithms have been prepared. Whether there is a significant difference among the experimental results obtained have been tested with the nonparametric Friedman test.

2.1. The Test Platform

2.1.1. The Structure of the Programming Languages Compared

C# is a general-purpose, type-safe, object-oriented programming language. The purpose of programming language should be to improve the efficiency of the programmer. This purpose programming language balances performance, expressiveness and simplicity. The C# language is platform-neutral, but it was written to work well with the Microsoft .NET Framework [9].

On April 15, 2014 Embarcadero released RAD Studio XE6 which included Delphi XE6 and C++Builder. It allows creating natively compiled apps for all platforms for both desktop and mobile, and even wearable devices like Google Glass, with a single C++ or Object Pascal (Delphi) codebasing. RAD Studio XE6 adds support for Android 4.4 KitKat. It also became possible to create FireMonkey mobile apps for Android [10].

Python is a popular programming language that can develop both independent and script applications. Python is a portable, strong, easy-to-use, and free programming language. Python is an object-oriented, interpreted, modular, and interactive programming language. Its indentation-based simple syntax facilitates learning and remembering it. Thus, it allows starting programming without wasting any time in the details of syntax. It supports modular structure, class system, and any input field. It is compatible with almost all platforms (e.g. Unix, Linux, Mac, Windows, Amiga, Symbian Os). Python allows developing software in many fields such as systems programming, user interface (GUI) programming, web programming, application, and database software programming [11].

2.1.2 The Computer Properties

The features of the computer used in the performance test are as in the following:

- Dell N series Notebook
- Hard Disc: 700 Gigabyte
- RAM: 6 Gigabyte
- Processor: Intel I7 2670QM 2.20 Gigahertz
- Operation System: Windows 7 Professional

2.2. Workloads

The concept of workload is very important in modeling of computer systems [12]. The performance evaluation using workload reduces quantity and cost of simulation [13]. Experimental system evaluations generally include workload programs. Every performance evaluation program is worked with systems having different properties. The behavior of the system is measured and its performance is interpreted [14]. Workload includes a list of services that should be fulfilled by the system [2]. Workloads in this study are made up of different programs. Each of these programs measures a different property of the programming language. These workloads are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Workloads

Workload Code	Explanation
Hello [1]	Printing of "Hello World" on the screen for 5000 times
Matrix [2]	Multiplication of two matrices of 500 x 500 dimensions
Sorting [3]	Sorting of the series with 10000 elements, the element values of which are in the worst situation with the Selection Sorting algorithm.
Sieve [4]	Estimation of the prime numbers at the interval of [1..8193] with the sieve algorithm for 10.000 times
Empty Cycle [5]	The empty cycle at the interval of [1.. 100000000]
Mean [6]	Estimation of the mean of the numbers at the interval of [1..3000] for 30000 times
Table [7]	Writing and Reading of the character knowledge "abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz1234567890abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz1234567890abcdefg" with a text file for 10000 times

The algorithms used as workloads have been coded in every language the performance of which will be tested by using standard properties in a way that they are equal to each other. These program codes have been converted into executable code (.exe) and their memory consumptions and response times have been obtained from Windows 7 Command Prompt.

The Hello [1] program tests writing on the screen and loading performance of the program, Matrix [2] and Mean [6] programs integer arithmetic performance, Sorting [3] program cycle and logical decision performance. The Sieve [4] program to predict prime numbers by using the classical Sieve Eratosthenes algorithm. The Sieve program tests the basic logical comparison and integer arithmetic operation [15]. The Empty Cycle [5] program tests the loop performance of programming languages. Table [7] program tests reading in the text file and writing performance. [16].

2.3. Performance Metrics

Metrics used in the performance tests are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Performance Metrics Used In The Performance Tests

Metrics of Performance	
1	Length of Code (LOC or CLOC)
2	Time of Response (ms-mili second)
3	Memory Usege (KB (kilobyte))

2.3.1. The Code Length of the Programs Written

The number of the code is commonly used in order to measure the source code length of a program. (LOC (line of code)) [17]. It is completed as $LOC=NLOCK+CLOCK$. NLOCK (Uncommented Source Line of Code) is a code line which is not used during compilation. A Commented Source Line of Code (CLOCK) is a code line which is used during compilation. The best prediction should generally be performed as in the following in order to prediction the source code length of a program.

1. Blank lines
2. Compiled lines (CLOC)
3. Data (variable, constant) definitions and other commands
4. Lines produced by the programming language

The density of the lines compiled can be calculated with $CLOC*100/LOC$ formula [18]. The line numbers of program codes used as a workload in this study have been calculated in line with the explanations stated above and they have been shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Code Lengths of the Programs Written

Test	C# 2013 .net					Delphi XE6				
	CL*	Data Definitions	Produced by the Language	L*	CL/L (%)	CL*	Data Definition	Produced by the Language	L*	CL/L (%)
Hello [1]	6	0	11	17	35	5	1	8	14	36
Matrix [2]	19	5	11	35	54	19	3	8	30	63
Sorting [3]	19	2	11	32	59	16	2	8	26	62
Sieve [4]	25	5	11	41	61	31	3	8	42	74
Empty Cycle [5]	4	1	11	16	25	5	2	8	15	33
Mean [6]	12	3	11	26	46	13	2	8	23	57
Table [7]	18	4	11	33	55	22	5	8	35	63
Mean					48					55
Test	Python 3.4									
	CL*	Data Definitions	Produced by the Language	L*	CL/L (%)					
Hello [1]	5	1	0	6	83					
Matrix [2]	12	4	0	16	75					
Sorting [3]	11	2	0	13	85					
Sieve [4]	14	6	0	20	70					
Empty Cycle [5]	5	1	0	6	83					
Mean [6]	8	1	0	9	89					
Table [7]	14	1	0	15	93					
Mean					83					

* L:LOC CL:CLOC

The graphic of CLOC/LOC values given in Table III are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Compiled Line density graphic (CLOC/LOC)

2.3.2. Time of Response

The concept of response time is very important in computer systems performance test studies. Response time is the measurement of the time for which a user or an application has to wait until a command requested is completed [12]. In this study, response times of workloads run in the programming languages desired to be measured are given in Table 4.

Table 4. Response Time of Workloads on Windows Operation System (ms-millisecond)

Test	C# 2013			Delphi XE6			Python 3.4		
	Min	Max	Mean	Min	Max	Mean	Min	Max	Mean
Hello [1]	218	749	413	343	483	379	318	1117	591
Matrix [2]	2308	2511	2436,3	592	624	602,3	71820	80085	75181
Sorting [3]	265	327	283,5	280	327	305,5	27262	28204	27749,1
Sieve [4]	1076	1154	1101	920	1092	984,2	32196	32863	32288,5
Empty Loop [5]	358	436	381,6	312	374	333,9	10094	10693	10345,1
Mean [6]	374	421	405,2	312	359	330,7	16140	16927	16382,4
Table [7]	15	31	24,6	109	156	114	133	279	187,5
Mean			720,7			435,6			23246,4

Figure 2. Response Time Graphic of Workloads

Mean response times for all workloads are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Mean Response Times for All the Workloads by the Programming Languages

2.3.3. Memory Consumption

Memory consumption of every workload has been obtained separately by programming languages by using Windows Task Manager. These values are shown as Kilobyte (KB) in Table 5

Table 5. Memory Consumption (KB)

Workload	C# 2013	Delphi XE6	Python 3.4
Hello [1]	1,5	0,7	2,3
Matrix [2]	4,2	3,6	2,3
Sorting [3]	1,4	0,7	2,5
Sieve [4]	1,4	0,7	2,4
Empty Loop [5]	1,4	0,7	2,3
Mean [6]	1,4	0,7	2,3
Table [7]	4,4	0,7	2,7
Mean	2,2	1,1	2,4

The graphic belonging to memory consumption data is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Memory Consumption Graphic

2.4. Statistical Design

Minimal descriptive statistics contains the following for a data set: total observation number, mean, median, standard deviation, minimal value, maximum value and number of observations. Presentation of descriptive statistics data on dependent variable is significant [16, 19]. One-Way ANOVA is used when searching the effect of one independent variables on a dependent variable [20]. In this study, the dependent variable is response time, the independent variable is programming languages. Significant results have been obtained by applying one-way ANOVA on these dependent and independent variables. However, because variance equality assumption has not been ensured, these results have not been presented in the article. Instead, the Friedman test, a non-parametric method, has been used.

The Friedman test is the non-parametric correspondence of one-way ANOVA test. When the same samples belonging to the subjects have been treated and when these samples have been measured at three or more points, the Friedman test is used [20, 21].

The Friedman test has been used in order to find whether there is a significant difference among response times obtained as a result of running of every workload on C# 2013, Delphi XE6 and Python 3.4 programming languages. The Friedman test showed that there is a significant difference between the response times of 3 different programming languages in all workloads except for Hello[1]. The test data obtained from the Friedman test are shown in Table 6. In addition, mean rank values and the general average of these values clearly indicate that Delphi XE6 is the fastest programming language in terms of response time. Statistical results regarding Hello[1] demonstrate that there is no significant difference for this workload in terms of response time, $\chi^2(2) = 1.4, p > .05$.

Table 6. The Friedman Test Data

Wordload	Mean Rank			<i>p</i>	χ^2	df
	C# 2013	Delphi XE6	Python 3.4			
Hello [1]	1,90	1,8	2,30	0,49	1,4	2
Matrix [2]	2	1	3	0	20	
Sorting [3]	1,2	1,8	3	0	16,8	
Sieve [4]	1,95	1,05	3	0	19,54	
Empty Loop [5]	2	1	3	0	20	
Mean [6]	2	1	3	0	20	
Table [7]	1	2,1	2,9	0	18,2	
The average of the mean rank	1,72	1,39	2,89			

In this study, effect size was calculated, too. The calculation of effect size is important because it allows identifying the group(s) from which the significant difference between groups arises [20]. Following the Friedman test, the Wilcoxon signed rank test was used for calculating the effect sizes of the programming languages used. In this way, type 1 mistake was kept at minimum [22].

The Bonferroni correction value was calculated in order to calculate the significance coefficient of posthoc tests. The α /number of comparisons formula was applied to determine the significance value of Wilcoxon tests used for posthoc, according to Field (2005). New significance value was found to be $0.05/3=0.017$. Effect size (*r*) and significance value (*p*) obtained through the posthoc test are showed in Table VII.

The below-mentioned formula was used for calculating the effect size: [23].

$$r = Z/\sqrt{N}$$

r: Effect size, *Z*: Z value, *N*: N_1+N_2

Table 7. The Posthoc Test Data

Wordload	Post Hoc									
	Delphi XE6-C# 2013			Python 3.4-C# 2013			Python 3.4-DelphiXE6			
	<i>Z</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>Z</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>Z</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>p</i>	
Matrix [2]	-2,81	-0,63	0,005	-2,8	-0,63	0,005	-2,80	-0,63	0,005	N
Sorting [3]	-2,02	-0,45	0,043	-2,8	-0,63	0,005	-2,8	-0,63	0,005	
Sieve [4]	-2,67	-0,60	0,008	-2,8	-0,63	0,005	-2,8	-0,63	0,005	
Empty Loop [5]	-2,82	-0,63	0,005	-2,8	-0,63	0,005	-2,8	-0,63	0,005	
Mean [6]	-2,82	-0,63	0,005	-2,8	-0,63	0,005	-2,8	-0,63	0,005	
Table [7]	-2,85	-0,64	0,004	-2,8	-0,63	0,005	-2,7	-0,60	0,007	
The average of the r		-0,60			-0,63			-0,63		

An effect size (*r*) closer to zero means a lower insignificant difference between the response times of programming languages. However, *p* and *r* values in the Table VII indicate that the difference between binary groups is big enough to be considered significant. However, Hello [1] workload is ignored here. This is because; the Friedman test also indicated no significant difference in this

workload. The average effect sizes (r) for all workloads also demonstrate that the difference between binary groups is big enough to be considered significant. In other words, the difference between the programming languages in terms of response time is big and statistically significant.

3. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The general averages of the response times related to all workloads obtained from the performance tests indicate that Delphi XE6 is considerably faster than C# 2013 and Python. Also Delphi XE6 is 3 times as fast as C# 2013 and 49 times as fast as Python. However, C# 2013 writes and reads text file averagely 4.5 times as fast as Delphi XE6. All these results are statistically significant in all workloads except for Hello [1]. Thus, the results concerning this test are not interpreted here.

The detailed comparison of the response times of the programming languages by workload shows the results given below.

The general averages of the response times regarding Matrix [2] and Average [6] workloads indicate that Delphi XE6 is almost 3 times as fast as C# 2013. This result shows that the integer arithmetic performance of Delphi XE6 is faster than that of C# 2013.

The results concerning Sort [3] workload indicate that C# is 1.07 times as fast as Delphi XE6 in logical decision performance. The results related to Sieve [4] workload, which tests basic integer arithmetic and logical comparison, point out that Delphi XE6 is 1.1 times as fast as C# 2013. C# 2013 is faster only in logical decision performance. However, when both logical decision and integer arithmetic come into play, Delphi XE6 is faster.

Delphi XE6 is 1.14 times as fast as C# 2013 in terms of loop performance.

In terms of response time, Python remains falls behind the other two languages in all tests. Consequently, the programs written in Python run much slower than those written in C# 2013 and Delphi XE6.

In terms of memory usage, Delphi XE6 uses 50% less memory than C# 2013 and almost 54% less memory than Python. That is to say, the programs coded in Delphi XE6 can run faster by using less memory.

Although Delphi XE6 is strong in terms of memory usage, it is weaker than Python and slightly stronger than C# 2013 in terms of code density. The averages of compiled code density obtained from all tests show that Python is the strongest. The averages of compiled code density of Python, Delphi XE6, and C# 2013 are 83%, 55%, and 48% respectively. These figures indicate that code density not used by Python during compilation is low. In other words, Python does not produce many codes other than the program codes to be used for solving the problem. Delphi XE6 is stronger than C# 2013 in terms of code density.

4. CONCLUSION

Delphi XE6 is considerably faster than C# 2013 and Python 3.4 in terms of response time. Python is stronger than the other two languages only in terms of code density. Delphi XE6 uses 50% less memory than C# 2013 and almost 54% less memory than Python. That is to say, the programs coded in Delphi XE6 can run faster by using less memory.

When all performance measurements are considered, Delphi XE6 is seen to be stronger than the other two languages. The present study proved that statistically.

Python is quite weak in terms of both memory usage and response time. However, Python is distinctive relative to C# 2013 and Delphi XE6 in that it has an indentation-based simple syntax, is compatible with different platforms (e.g. Linux, Pardus, Windows), and is free.

REFERENCES

- [1] Blackburn, S. M., McKinley, K. S., e.g., “Wake Up and Smell the Coffee :Evaluation Methodology for the 21st Century”, *Communications of the ACM*, 51:83-89, (2008).
- [2] Dick ,J.R., Kent, K. B. And Libby, J. C., “A quantitative analysis of the .NET common language runtime”, *Journal of Systems Architecture*, 54:679–696, (2008).
- [3] Wikipedi World Wide Web site, http://tr.wikipedia.org/wiki/.NET_Framework
- [4] Fourment, M., Gillings, M. R., “A comparison of common programming languages used in bioinformatics”, *BMC Bioinformatics*, 9(82):1-9, (2008).
- [5] Arudchelvam, T., Wijayakulasooriya, J., Hoole, S. R. H., “Comparison of Performance of Finite Element Codes in Different Programming Languages Converted From Legacy Finite Element Codes”, 3rd International Conference on Electronics, Biomedical Engineering and its Applications (ICEBEA'2013), Singapore, 147-151 , (2013).
- [6] Prechelt, L., “An empirical comparison of seven programming languages” ,*Computer*, 33: 23 – 29, (2000).
- [7] Berlin K. , Mary Jacob, J., Kochhar, G. , eg., “Evaluating the Impact of Programming Language Features on the Performance of Parallel Applications on Cluster Architectures”, *Languages and Compilers for Parallel Computing Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, 2958:194-208, (2004).
- [8] Juristo, N., Moreno, A., *Basics of Software Engineering Experimentation*, Kluwer Academic , South America, Boston, (2001).
- [9] Albahari, J., Albahari , B., *C# 5.0 in a Nutshell, Fifth Edition*, O’Reilly Media, O’Reilly Media, Inc, United States of America, (2012).
- [10] Wikipedi World Wide Web site, [Online]. Available: [http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Delphi_\(programming_language\)#cite_note-23](http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Delphi_(programming_language)#cite_note-23)
- [11] [Online]. Available:<http://pythontr.org/forum/5-gr/7-python-nedir.html>
- [12] Fortier, P., Michel, H., *Computer Systems Performance Evaluation and Prediction*, Digital Pres, USA, Burlington, (2003).
- [13] Conte, T. M., Hwu, W., “Benchmark Characterization”, *System Sciences, Proceedings of the Twenty-Fourth Annual Hawaii International Conference on*, 1:364-372, (1991).
- [14] Conte, T. M., Hwu, W., “Benchmark Characterization for Experimental System Evaluation”, *Proc. Hawaii Int'l Conf. System Science I*, 6-18, (1990).
- [15] Morin, R. C., *Managed C# versus Unmanaged C++* (2009): [Online]. Available::<http://www.csharp4help.com/archives2/archive458.html>
- [16] Karacı, A., “Performance Comparison of Managed C# and Delphi Prism in Visual Studio and Unmanaged Delphi 2009 and C++ Builder 2009 Languages”, *International Journal of Computer Applications*, 26(1): 9-15, (2011).
- [17] ŞAHİN, M., “Java, Python Ve Ruby Dillerinin Performans Karşılaştırması”, *Akademik Bilişim 2007*, Dumlupınar University, Kütahya, 529-532,(2007)
- [18] Chiş, M., “Evolutionary Decision Trees and Software Metrics for Module Defects Identification”, *Proceedings Of World Academy Of Science, Engineering And Technology*, 28:273-277, (2008).
- [19] Emam, K. El, *A Methodology for Validating Software Product Metrics*, National Research Council of Canada, Ottawa, Ontario, Canada NCR/ERC-1076, (2000).
- [20] Kalaycı, Ş., *SPSS Uygulamalı Çok Değişkenli İstatistik Teknikleri*, Asil Yayın Dağıtım, Turkey, Ankara, (2008).
- [21] Sá, J.M., *Applied Statistics Using SPSS, STATISTICA, MATLAB and R* , Springer Berlin Heidelberg, USA, Newyork, (2007).

- [22] Pallant, J., SPSS Survival Manual, Mc Graw Hill Open University Press, Newyork, (2007).
[23] Field, A. , Discovering Statistics using IBM SPSS Statistics , SAGE Publications, Washington DC, (2005).

Authors

Dr. (Mr.) Abdulkadir KARACI

Assistant professor

Department of Department of Computer Engineering

B.E. (Computer Education)

M.E. (Computer Education)

Ph.D (Electronic and Computer Education)

Areas of Interest: Intelligent Tutoring System, Artificial Neural Network, Programming Language